

Intelligent screwdriver for personalized torque recommendations in orthopedic surgery

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Abstract: This project presents the development of an intelligent screwdriver designed to provide personalized torque recommendations during bone screw insertion. Using a model-based method, the system records torque and rotation signals to estimate patient-specific bone strength and uses this to provide a maximum safe torque limit. Two feedback mechanisms are proposed: visual indicators for surgeons or an electromechanical clutch to prevent over-tightening. A prototype, equipped with sensors and wireless communication, demonstrated the physical concept, while the mathematical aspects were tested and successfully predicted the stripping torque. Though further optimization is needed, the system effectively meets the specified device requirements and represents a significant advancement in patient-specific orthopedic tools.

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I. Introduction

Bone screws are used in a variety of orthopedic procedures for fracture [1] and implant fixation [2]. During these procedures, the tightening torque used for the screw can impact the outcomes of the surgery. If too tight, the screw may damage the threads formed in the bone, causing a weaker fixation that may be more likely to fail under load or shock [3]. If too loose, the screw may back out over time, compromising the fixation stability, or leading to loose implants/debris and other further damage [4].

In current surgical practice, screws are generally tightened ad-hoc, with the surgeon using their intuition, experience, and tactile feedback to determine the appropriate tightness. While surgeons are skilled professionals and this works adequately in many cases, it is still a subjective judgment, and may be impacted by human factors like stress and fatigue, and less experienced or skilled surgeons may not achieve the same fixation quality as more skilled ones [5]. Hence, an automated torque determination system may be useful in a traditional operating theater to ease the load on surgeons, and provide a more objective level of torquing. Additionally, with the advent of automated, semi-automated, or robot-assisted surgery, surgeons may no longer directly/physically control tightening operations, necessitating a computational method for torque-control.

This project addresses the following key research questions:

1. How tight should a bone screw be?
2. How can personalized torque recommendations be provided during surgery in an intelligent and scientific way?
3. How can this system meet surgical device requirements, such as sterilizability?

This research explores a system for personalized torque recommendations during surgery, integrating real-time data to adapt to patient-specific bone properties. We present the development of an intelligent bone screwdriver that can predict maximum safe torque and discuss its practical implementation in the operating room.

II. Material and methods

To answer these research questions, a model-based method with parameter identification was developed. The torque and rotation signals during screw insertion were recorded to assess the strength of the bone, which can vary significantly between patients. The system assumes that the screw's geometry and material properties are known, while the unknown variable is the bone strength.

Using this system, the maximum safe torque is determined by a forward model [6] based on strengths determined from recorded insertion dynamics using an inverse model [7], [8], [9], [10]. The method involves:

- **Instrumentation:** Torque and rotation are measured during screw insertion using strain gauges and gyroscopes.
- **Data Collection:** Signals are transmitted via Bluetooth or WiFi, enabling real-time external monitoring and analysis.
- **Torque Calculation:** An inverse model processes the signals to estimate the bone's strength, and then a forward model determines the maximum safe torque for screw insertion.

The system could use one or both of two main approaches for implementing the torque limit in surgical practice:

- **Visual Indicators:** Green/red LEDs signal whether the torque limit has been reached, leaving

the final decision to the surgeon. Or an external display can relay more complex data.

- **Electromechanical Clutch:** Automatically prevents further tightening once the torque limit is reached, ensuring the screw is not over-tightened.

III. Results and discussion

A prototype of the intelligent screwdriver system was developed, integrating sensors and communication systems for real-time monitoring and data processing. The full integration has not been thoroughly tested, however the system is minimally functional and can integrate with the current prototype data processing software [11].

The mathematical modelling was also tested using a test stand [12], and successfully predicted the stripping torque [13], [14], which is the torque at which the bone-screw interface begins to fail. The model's predictions correlated well with actual values, demonstrating the feasibility of using a model-based approach to personalize torque recommendations.

However, the model is not without limitations. While the predictions were generally accurate, improvements could be made to ensure the points lie on a more consistent line, thereby enhancing the precision of the predictions. The performance of the system could be further optimized through:

- Better calibration of sensors.
- Advanced data processing algorithms.
- Refining the forward model to account for more variables related to bone quality.

The prototype can also meet sterilizability requirements by being designed for single-use, pre-sterilized deployment, although some additional steps in sealing the device and choosing correct materials remain. The use of electronic components, particularly batteries, pose challenges for autoclave sterilization, making single-use designs more practical.

IV. Conclusions

This research demonstrated the feasibility of an intelligent screwdriver capable of personalizing torque recommendations during surgery. By recording torque and rotation signals in real-time and using a model-based method, the system provides safe torque limits tailored to the patient's bone strength, though further refinements in the model are necessary to enhance precision. The choice between visual or electromechanical feedback systems allows flexibility for surgeon preference during the future development.

The project achieved its primary objectives by successfully developing a prototype to demonstrate the technology. Although there is room for improvement, this system represents a significant advancement toward intelligent, patient-specific surgical tools in orthopedic procedures. Future work will focus on refining the model and optimizing the prototype for wider clinical use, especially in terms of regulatory requirements, achieving sterilizability, and user interface design.

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